

THE CONTENT OF THEIR ACTIVITIES ACCORDING TO THE PSYCHODIAGNOSTIC NATURE OF THE AMTXAUER INTELLIGENCE TEST, WHICH IS PART OF THE INTELLIGENCE TESTS

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ABSTRACT

In Uzbekistan. M.Davletshin, E.Goziev, B.R.Kadyrov, M.Vohidov, V.M.Karimova, Z.T.Nishanova, K.B.Kadyrov, E.Z.Usmanova, T.S.Jo 'ryev, J.X.Mavlonov, Sh.R.Samarov, A.F.Azimovas and others conducted their scientific research on the issues of mental ability, interest, motive, talent, talent. The availability of the ability to qualify students with a high level of intelligence and intelligence in studies using intellectual tests and other psychodiagnostic techniques can conveniently and easily master the knowledge, skills and competencies given to these qualified students and successfully apply the acquired skills in practice.

Key words: *intelligence, psychological testing, nonverbal scale, amtxauer intelligence test.*

INTRODUCTION

According to scientific psychological sources, intelligence is derived from the Latin word, which usually means more intelligent understanding, understanding, understanding. It seems to us that intelligence consists in the structure of a complex of a person's to some extent solid, stable mental abilities. Many classical tests have been playing an important role in determining an individual's level of intelligence.

It is advisable to note that the phenomena of immediacy in human intellectual development are not only explained by the properties of the material base, but also the hesitant "natural and artificial" sources of the material base and the main factor in exchange for the emergence of the field of perception, the emergence of an "artificial" system, spatial connections, the fuller use of biological and psychological capabilities. The methodology consists of 9 sections, each section has 16-20 assignments. The assignment statement and solution sample are given before each section. Each section sets a fixed time to work with assignments.

We conducted an experiment using the H Amtxauer methodology. The study involved 120 students..

Table 1.

Student performance according to the amtxauer methodology

Test scales	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Indicators in percentages	78%	74%	53%	64%	52%	48%	52%	59%	62%

1. picture. Student performance according to the amtxauer methodology

Performing subtests of the amtxauer methodology has been a challenge for some readers. We attributed this state to the fact that students did not face such assignments before, and the necessary skills were not formed. In the period when the development of today's society makes great demands on the intellectual potential of young people, this indicator is definitely low. Since the student period, the formation of knowledge, concepts about non-standard assignments and the formation of skills and competencies in the performance of such assignments provides the basis for raising their intellectual potential to a higher level.

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